

Enhanced Fault Detection and Classification for Renewable-Integrated Three Terminal Transmission Systems

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Abstract. Three terminal transmission lines offers a greater flexibility in power transmission, but the complex structure leads to greater challenges in protecting them. In order to ensure the safety of these lines, distance relays are crucial for the rapid and precise detection of faults, thereby ensuring system stability. However, there are many difficulties with distance relays, especially when it comes to fault detection in three terminal systems. The difficulties of distance relays in three terminal transmission lines are investigated in this study, with a focus on fault detection and section identification. A novel protection technique is developed, utilising the Covariance of Superimposed Three-Phase Instantaneous Active Power approach (COSTIAP) to improve fault detection precision and section identification. The covariance coefficients of currents are used to classify the fault types. The proposed method is completely a time domain technique which requires only the voltage and current signals that are extracted at the relay without any need for signal processing. Additionally, a wind farm integration is taken into consideration to further study the effectiveness of the suggested algorithm. Also, different operational conditions like capacitor switching, load switching are also considered for validation of the proposed method. The results demonstrate that the algorithm improves the reliability of the distance relay system in different operational conditions and fault circumstances.

Keywords: Teed Networks, Transmission lines Protection, Superimposed Components, Covariance, Section Identification, Fault Classification, Wind Integration.

1. Introduction

The reliability of electrical networks is significantly influenced by faults in transmission lines, which can lead to blackouts, interruptions in industrial processes, and cascading outages. [1, 2]. According to the available literature, numerous methods for identifying the faulty region and safeguarding the healthy one have been developed. These methods can broadly be classified as time domain, frequency domain, intelligence domain techniques. The frequency domain techniques involve the transformation of time domain signal into other frequency domains using a transform technique like Fourier Transform, Wavelet Transform and S-Transform, Hilbert Hung Transform. The methodology suggested in [3] uses

calculation of fundamental phasors of voltage and current using Fourier Transform to identify the type of fault occurred. However, these methods exhibit sensitivity to system transients and encounter challenges in accurately detecting faults with high resistance or those located near the PMU. Moreover, exclusive reliance on phasor data may pose challenges during power swings or in the context of inverter-based resources (IBRs) [4]. Wavelet Transform on the other hand provides better time-frequency localization compared to Fourier transforms, allowing for more accurate fault detection and classification [5]. S Transform performs even better than Wavelet Transform as they have the capability of multi-resolution and phase preservation [6].

The use of intelligence technique like ANN, SVM, RBF, k-NN and Fuzzy Logic Systems [10] also offers a promising solution to transmission line protection. A multilayer Perceptron feed forward neural network with back propagation algorithm is proposed in [7] to classify and locate the faults on transmission lines. An accurate method for detection, classification and localization of faults occurring in power transmission lines using Artificial Neural Network (ANN) is presented in [8] in which Power transmission system was modelled in DlgSILENT PowerFactory. The power system faults are detected and classified with a quarter cycle data of power frequency using a SVM based technique in [9-10]. An RBF based fault location method using hyperbolic S-Transform is detailed in [11] which is less immune to noise compared to wavelet transform. An RBF that does not require pre-defined thresholds for fault identification is proposed in [12]. A fuzzy logic-based fault classification approach using current samples only is presented in [13]. The fault occurrence time and the faulty phases are determined by finding the distance between each sample and its fifth nearest neighbour in a pre-default window using k-NN [14]. Also, some deep learning algorithms like CNN [15] and LSTM [16] are applied to find the faults in power systems. But these methods require a huge data set for training purpose. Also, they suffer from difficulties in identifying new data patterns which are not present in training data.

A new method for fault detection, fault section identification and fault classification without using any intelligent tools or signal processing methods is presented in this paper. The proposed technique called COSTIAP (Covariance based Superimposed Three-phase Instantaneous Active power) is based entirely on time domain analysis using a statistical approach employing a sample-based system. COSTIAP technique uses voltage and current data collected from each end relay. The COTIAP technique can distinguish between normal operating conditions like capacitor switching, load switching and fault conditions by comparing the active power and current covariance indices. This approach has been tested in a MATLAB/SIMULINK environment for a three-terminal power transmission network that incorporates wind farms.

This paper is organized as follows: In Section 2 the details of the model studied are provided, the details of COSTIAP are discussed in section 3. The proposed methodology is detailed in Section 4 and Section 5 provides the simulation results. Conclusions are presented in Section 6.

2. Three Terminal Transmission System Integrated with Wind Farm

Three terminal transmission lines offers a wide range of advantages over two terminal lines. The integration of renewable energy sources like solar or wind power to the power grid in a three terminal network is much easier compared to two terminal lines. A 230 kV, 50 Hz three-terminal transmission network is considered and modelled using the MATLAB/SIMULINK software. It consists of three sections with different length of transmission as shown in Figure 1. A 100MW wind farm is integrated into the model at terminal 3. Using the DFIG technology proposed in [17], the wind farm is integrated into the system.

Figure-1. A 230 kV, 50 Hz three terminal transmission network with wind farm

A full cycle data of voltage and current are required for the analysis. This requires a sample window of size 20ms for a 50Hz supply system. The proposed approach is tested by simulating several faults scenarios, with different values for fault distance, resistance, and inception time. The influence of critical events like capacitor and load switching are also studied.

3. Covariance of Superimposed Three-Phase Active Power (COSTIAP) method

Covariance is the measure of the deviation of each individual value from the mean within a dataset. To find the variance coefficient equation (1) is used where "x" is a value in the dataset, "μ" is the average value of all the data points, and "N" is the sum of all the data points.

$$X = \sum \frac{(x - \mu)^2}{N - 1} \tag{1}$$

The covariance calculation is similarly applied to the active power signal, which can be represented using equation (2) and (3).

$$p(t) = v(t) \cdot i(t) = 0.5 * Vm \cdot Im \{ \cos\theta (1 - \cos 2\omega t) + \sin\theta \cdot \sin 2\omega t \} \tag{2}$$

$$p(t) = va(t) \cdot ia(t) + vb(t) \cdot ib(t) + vc(t) \cdot ic(t) \tag{3}$$

Now, to calculate the active power we require the instantaneous voltage and current signals which are expressed using equations (4) and (5)

$$v(t) = V_m \sin(\omega t) \quad (4)$$

$$i(t) = I_m \sin(\omega t + \theta) \quad (5)$$

Finally, the covariance coefficient of active power signal is calculated using (6), in which $P3\varphi_i$ is the three-phase active power calculated using equation (2) and (3).

$$\text{COSP}3\varphi_i = \sum_{n=1}^N \frac{((P3\varphi_i - \mu_i)^2)}{N-1} \quad (6)$$

4. Proposed Fault Detection & Section Identification Algorithm

A Covariance based algorithm is proposed for fault detection, section identification and classification on a three terminal transmission system integrated with a wind farm at one terminal. It requires the super imposed voltage and current signals which are calculated using equation (7) and (8), where, V_{scn} , I_{scn} represent the superimposed voltage & current components and V_n & I_n are measured voltage & current signal for the n th phase, suffix n represents the phases A, B & C respectively, k represents the $(2N)$ th sampling instant and N specifies the number of samples over one cycle.

$$V_{scn}(k+1-N:k) = V_n(k+1-N:k) - V_n(k+1-2N:k-N) \quad (7)$$

$$I_{scn}(k+1-N:k) = I_n(k+1-N:k) - I_n(k+1-2N:k-N) \quad (8)$$

Now, the three phase active powers at all the three terminals are calculated using equation (3). Using the power coefficients the COSTPAP values are computed. If the values of COSTPAP are greater than a threshold value, then there is a fault occurred in the system. Based on the COSTIAP values the faulty section is identified. If any section has greater COSTIAP value compared to other, then that section is identified as faulted section. Following the faulty section identification, the type of fault is identified by using the covariance coefficients of all the phase currents. If any phase current covariance coefficients are greater than a predefined threshold, then that phase is under fault. The detailed flowchart of the proposed algorithm is depicted in Figure 3.

5. Simulation Results

The system shown in Figure 1 is simulated against various events like faults, capacitor switching and load switching. One cycle data of voltage and current signals are extracted. The superimposed components of voltage and current are calculated to find the COSTIAP coefficients. Based on the magnitude of these coefficients all the critical events are classified. Firstly, the coefficients are compared for fault detection, later for section identification and finally for fault classification.

5.1 Fault Detection and Section Identification

A single line to ground fault at 30km distance from terminal 1 is simulated with a fault resistance of 50Ω for the system shown in Figure 2. The superimposed voltage and currents are calculated. The COSTIAP coefficients for all the three terminals are obtained using equation (6) and the corresponding plots are shown in Figure 3. Under normal operational circumstances, the values are below the 'Thr' threshold. Following the beginning of the line-to-ground fault at terminal 1, the COSTIAP indices of terminal 1 raises above the threshold and indices of terminal 2 and 3 are below the threshold.

Figure 2. Flow chart of the proposed algorithm

Figure 3. COSTIAP indices for LG (AG) fault at terminal-1.

On the similar lines, a LLG fault is simulated at terminal-2 for the system as shown in Figure 1. The corresponding COSTIAP indices are plotted in Figure 4 which indicates the fault occurrence in section 2. Also, a LL fault is simulated in section 3 and the resulting waveforms are shown in Figure 5. The graphs indicate that the fault occurred in section 3.

Figure 4. COSTIAP indices for LLG (BCG) fault at terminal-2.

Figure 5. COSTIAP indices for LL (AB) fault at terminal-3.

The results indicate that the COSTIAP method of fault detection and section identification gives accurate results in identifying the faulty sections. After the faulty section is identified the fault classification task is performed using the covariance indices of phase currents. The fault classification details are provided in the next section.

5.2 Fault Classification

Once the faulty section is identified, the phase currents of that section are used to calculate the covariance indices. If fault is present in any phase, then that phase current covariance indices will be greater than the threshold value. The proposed method is tested against various fault events and the details are given below.

Case 1: Single Line-Ground Fault

For instance, a single line to ground fault (BG) is simulated at 100km distance in section 1 for the system shown in Figure 1. The corresponding fault indices are shown in Figure 6, where the fault indices of phase B and Ground are above the threshold and remaining phase current indices are far below the threshold.

Figure 6. Covariance indices of Phase Currents for BG Fault.

Case 2: Double Line-Ground Fault

A double line to ground fault (ABG) is simulated at 50km distance in section 1 for the system shown in Figure 1. The corresponding fault indices are shown in Figure 7, where the fault indices of phases A, B and Ground are above the threshold and remaining phase current indices are far below the threshold.

Figure. 7. Covariance indices of Phase Currents for ABG Fault.

Case 3: Line-Line Fault

A line-line fault (BC) is simulated at 120km distance in section 1 for the system shown in Figure 1. The corresponding fault indices are shown in Figure 8, where the fault indices of phases B and C are above the threshold and remaining phase current indices are far below the threshold.

Figure. 8. Covariance indices of Phase Currents for BC Fault.

Case 4: Symmetrical Fault

A three-phase fault (ABC) is simulated at 170km distance in section 1 for the system shown in Figure 1. The corresponding fault indices are shown in Figure 9, where the fault indices of phases A, B and C are above the threshold and remaining phase current indices are far below the threshold.

Figure. 9. Covariance indices of Phase Currents for ABC Fault.

4. Conclusion

In this paper a Covariance based Superimposed Three-Phase Active Power (COSTIAP) method is proposed to enhances fault detection in three terminal transmission lines with renewable integration. Using the superimposed voltage and current components, the three-phase active power is calculated and covariance indices are estimated to detect faults. The proposed method can detect the faults within a single cycle. Also, it eliminates the need for additional filtering or complex computations as it is completely dependaa on time domain only. Following the faulty section identification, the fault are classified based on the current covariance coefficients. Furthermore, the COSTIAP ensures precise accuracy in differentiating the faulty events from other operational conditions like capacitor switching and load switching. The proposed method is immune to noise and offers a simpler and computationally efficient solution, making it more suitable for power system protection.

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